

AT 2041-2047

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.172 Max: 62.223	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1392 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		
				In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
DEFINITION imbrex tube - coffin for grave # 43				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1461	Filled by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1460, 1463	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal		Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles		<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine		<input type="checkbox"/> Ash			
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae		<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone		<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones		Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia		<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt		<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)		<input type="checkbox"/> Clay		<input type="checkbox"/> Animal-teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar		<input type="checkbox"/> Sand		<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins		<input type="checkbox"/> Silt		<input type="checkbox"/> Shells			
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris		<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)					
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass							
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit							
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1458				Covers: 1459			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by: 1463, 1460				Fills: 1461			
OBSERVATIONS excavated by trowel, dry conditions. 2 tiles placed atop one another to make tube							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: central in area B, SU 1322 Shape: cylindrical							
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Two complete niches, on top of each other, used as burial container for an infant, probably a Neonatus. Both niches, the top and the bottom niches, got the same SU-number.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by T. Hart

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PDFd by BCR

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Entered by

on